

louis tomczyk

CANDIDATE FOR PH.D. OR POST DOCTORATE IN INTEGRATED PHOTONICS

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Personal Profile

I am a French photonics engineer having completed my PhD at one of France's leading institutions in telecommunications. During my PhD, I broadened my skills towards digital signal processing, artificial intelligence, and communications, I now wish to return to my core passion: physics and optics/photonics

Work Experience

Télécom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris

Palaiseau, France

PhD: Advanced monitoring techniques for optical telecommunications

Defended on 09/09/2025

- **Objective:** Development of algorithms to monitor the evolution of physical parameters (optical power, state of polarisation, laser phase noise, etc.) in coherent optical transmission systems to prevent network outages.
- Study and Matlab implementation of **Longitudinal Power Profile Estimators (LPPE)** based on nonlinear Kerr effects (SPM/XPM) combined with chromatic dispersion and signal statistics. Demonstrated how signal “gaussianisation” enhances (SPM/XPM) efficiency but increases the risk of network failure, and proposed a mitigation method. Published at IEEE/OECC 2023 (Access : zenodo.org/records/17370010).
- Theoretical modelling of nonlinear–dispersion interactions through the proposed **Gaussian Linear Interference** model, deriving the power interference rate within a signal. Detailed in the PhD manuscript.
- Python implementation of adaptive **Finite Impulse Response (FIR)** filters using a **Kullback–Leibler Divergence (DKL)**–based loss function for channel equalisation. This approach enables convergence for high–order and probabilistically shaped constellations, while tracking polarisation drifts. Published at IEEE/ECOC 2024 (Access : zenodo.org/records/17370079), and extended to laser phase noise tracking, published at IEEE/JLT 2025 (Access : zenodo.org/records/17370222).

Télécom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris

Palaiseau, France

Assistant Professor

09/2022 –05/2025

- **Optics and Photonics:** Delivered lectures and laboratory sessions to first-year engineering students on free–space optics (diffraction, holography), lasers, and fibre propagation. My teaching materials are available at : zenodo.org/records/17371080.
- **Electronics:** Laboratory sessions on analogue filtering and analogue/digital conversion for first–year students.
- **Ecology:** Practical exercises introducing the Kaya equation to illustrate global energy and climate trends.

Academia

Paris, France

Private Tutor

09/2023 –05/2024

- Provided one-to-one tutoring in physics and mathematics for undergraduate students. (years 1–2): electromagnetism, thermodynamics, mechanics, diffusion processes, and real analysis.
- Delivered tailored physics courses for high–school students.

BKtel Photonics

Lannion, France

Laser Engineer (Apprenticeship)

09/2020 –08/2021

- Design, fabrication, and testing of high–power fibre lasers (20 [W] @ 1060 nm and 100 [W] @ 1040 [nm], CW).
- Development and characterisation of Erbium–Doped Fibre Amplifiers (C–band, 1530–1565 [nm]).
- Automation and measurement safety tools for production lines (Python, TeraTerm).
- Development of a setup to measure the M^2 beam quality factor.
- Defined product specifications and conducted customer demonstrations.

iXblue

Lannion, France

Intern

07/2019 –08/2019

- Optimised splicing of polarisation–maintaining fibres via inter–correlation profile analysis.
- Developed an automatic algorithm for PM fibre axis detection using image processing (Matlab).

Education

Télécom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris

Palaiseau, France

PhD in Optical Coherent Telecommunications

2022/04 - Current

- Theory of telecommunications: transmissions, detection and estimation theory: channel models modulations

Xidian University (西安电子科技大学)

Xi'an (西安), China

Academic semester

2021/09 - 2022/02

- Introduction to artificial intelligence: methodology, algorithms (NN, SVMs, regressions) and metrics

National School of Advanced Technologies and Science (ENSSAT)

Lannion, France

Engineering in optics and photonics (\equiv bachelor 3 + Master 1 & 2)

2017/09 - 2021/08

- **Optics and Photonics:** anisotropy, free space optics (diffraction, holography), guided optics (fibres, silicon photonics), laser physics (all types, noise), nonlinear optics, quantum mechanics/optics & atomistic, ray optics, semiconductor physics
- **Mathematics:** Complex analysis, Fourier Analysis, Partial differential equations, Probabilities and stochastic processes
- **Electronics and computational mathematics:** Analog electronics, Finite element methods, image processing.

César Baggio & Gustave Eiffel high schools

Lille & Armentières, France

Scientific Preparation school (\equiv bachelor 1& 2)

2014/09 - 2017/07

- **Physics:** analog electronics, electromagnetism & optics, mechanics, thermodynamics & fluid mechanics,
- **Mathematics:** real analysis, probabilities, (multi) linear algebra, (differential) geometry & topology
- **Engineering:** solid and material mechanics, automation and linear systems, industrial drawing, fabrication processes
- **Chemistry:** crystallography, kinetics, mineral chemistry

Quick explanations on French engineering system. Intensive and competitive national entrance exams to engineering school (“Écoles d’Ingénieur”) are prepared in the so-called “Classe Prépa” (Scientific Preparation school) held in high school buildings, not in universities, consisting in 2 or 3 years. This training is common to all “classical” engineers (>85%, [see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Classe_pr%C3%A9paratoire_aux_grandes_%C3%A9coles]) and consists in 40 hours of class per week divided into 10h (maths) -10h (physics/chemistry) -10h (engineering) -4h (Philosophy/English)+6h (exams).

University Projects

Noise propagation in optical telecommunication link with amplifier’s power failure

Palaiseau, France

Télécom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris

2023/03 - 2023/07

- Developing noise propagation model in an amplified optical telecommunication link presenting an impaired amplifier (EDFA). I showed that a power drop at the amplifier output increases the average noise power only when the gain-droop model is considered.

Reviewer for Optical Fiber Technology (Elsevier Journal)

Palaiseau, France

Télécom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris

- Reviewing several articles claiming using artificial intelligence techniques for diverse operations in optical communications.

Chairman at the 5th Junior Conference on Wireless and Optical communications

Palaiseau, France

Télécom Paris, Institut Polytechnique de Paris

- Organisation and animation of a junior conference on networks and communications destined to all the masters and 1st year PhDs in both Institut Polytechnique de Paris and Université Paris-Saclay: <https://hebergement.universite-paris-saclay.fr/jwoc/2023-2/>
- Creation of the website and the submission platform.
- Selection and reviewing of the papers.
- Selection and invitation of worldwide expert speakers.

Sorting fuzzy clustering algorithms’ performance

Xi’an (西安), China

Xidian University (西安电子科技大学)

2021/12 - 2022/07

- Imprecision and uncertainty in evidential clustering. Suggestion of formalism and standardisation of metrics to quantify a global performance of a soft-partitioning algorithm.

Laser noise reduction beyond the quantum limit

Lannion, France

National School of Advanced Technologies and Science (ENSSAT)

2021/05

- Study of laser noise reduction techniques beyond the shot noise (quantum limit) using squeezed states using acousto-optic modulator, Second Harmonics Generation and Optical Parametric Oscillators.

Skills

Programming Python, Matlab, \LaTeX & TikZ

Languages French (Native), English (B2/C1), Russian (A1/A2)

Achievements

- 2020 **Nonlinear optics**, Online Mooc: Coursera at <https://www.coursera.org/learn/physique-optique> *École Polytechnique*
- 2020 **Introduction to quantum mechanics**, Online mooc: FUN
at <https://www.fun-mooc.fr/fr/cours/introduction-a-la-physique-quantique/> *ENSTA Paris*
- 2021 **Machine learning**, Online Mooc: OpenClassroom at
<https://openclassrooms.com/fr/partners/centralesupelec> *CentraleSupélec*

Publications

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

Relaxing dispersion pre-distorsion constraints of receiver-based power profile estimators
Łouis Tomczyk, Élie Awwad, Pétrós Ramantanis, Cédric Ware
Opto-Electronics and Communications Conference (OECC), 2023

Blind state of polarisation monitoring using variational autoencoders-inspired adaptive filter
Łouis Tomczyk, Élie Awwad, Diane Prato, Cédric Ware
European Conference on Optical Communications (ECOC), 2024

JOURNALS

Blind Polarisation Demultiplexing and Carrier Recovery Using Variational AutoEncoder-Inspired Equaliser for Probabilistic Constellation Shaping in Optical Fibre Communications
louis tomczyk, Élie Awwad, Cédric Ware
J. Light. Tech. p. 15. 2025

Engagements

Télécom Paris

PhD representative

- PhD student legal and psychological support.

Palaiseau, France

2023-2024

Science popularisation : The golden number and the Penrose tiling

Sublimaths, Télécom Paris

- Introduction of sequences, geometry and testing hypothesis to mid/high-school children within a Math's popularisation club : Sublimaths
- From the Fibonacci sequence to Penrose tiling, children were led to build by themselves such titling. <https://zenodo.org/records/17370453>

Palaiseau, France

2023/12

Enssat Sans Frontières Association Étudiante

President

- Humanitarian project in Togo : electrifying a high school. ouest-france.fr/bretagne/lannion-22300/lannion-1-association-etudiante-agit-ici-et-la-bas-6663055
- Humanitarian project in Senegal : sending school furnitures. ouest-france.fr/bretagne/tregastel-22730/tregastel-des-etudiants-soutiennent-l-association-solidarite-senegal-6429517
- Inter-generation activities, school teaching etc. letelegramme.fr/cotes-d-armor/lannion-22300/span-classamorce-enssat-san-s-frontierespan-ces-etudiants-donnent-de-leur-temps-3350169.php

Lannion, France

2018-2020

National School of Advanced Technologies and Science (ENSSAT)

Foreign student host

- Welcoming and support into legal administrative procedures.

Lannion, France

2019-2021

Interests

Travelling alone Eastern and southern Asia, Middle east, Europe

Writing Wrote several poetry collections and essay ([vers-sans-blason.fr](https://www.vers-sans-blason.fr))

Psychology/Sociology

References

- Dr. Élie AWWAD** Associate professor at Télécom Paris. PhD supervisor. [mail: elie.awwad@telecom-paris.fr](mailto:elie.awwad@telecom-paris.fr)
- Dr. Stéphane TRÉBAOL** Associate professor at ENSSAT. Master supervisor. [mail: trebaol@enssat.fr](mailto:trebaol@enssat.fr)